

Factors leading to high levels of indiscipline cases among pupils: A case of selected secondary schools in Lusaka District, Zambia

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Abstract

Indiscipline among pupils refers to a situation in which pupils do not control their behavior or obey school rules. Indiscipline entails any act that diverges from acceptable societal norms and values. It is a violation of school rules and regulations which is capable of obstructing the smooth and orderly functioning of the school system. Discipline in a classroom situation, is the ability to guide and control the class towards the attainment of predetermined objectives of education, while Indiscipline on the other hand entails a situation whereby energy and impulses are uncontrolled by moral principles or external authority. To this end, indiscipline in a school may be defined as the unwillingness of pupils and staff to respect authority, obey school rules and regulations, and maintain a high standard of moral and attitudinal behavior conducive to the teaching-learning process as essential to the smooth running of the school. It was for this aim that the study was conducted to analyze factors that lead to a high level of indiscipline among pupils in secondary schools of Lusaka district. The study employed a mixed-method approach and a descriptive survey design that sampled head teachers, teachers, and pupils. Data was obtained from the respondents by means of interviews and questionnaires. The sample consisted of three hundred respondents. Percentages, tables, graphs, and pie charts were used to analyze the data with a combination of software MS Access and MS Excel (version 26). The results of the analysis showed that pupils and teachers agreed on the causes and effects of indiscipline cases in secondary schools which included among others; the Influence of peers, Negative attitudes towards education, Irresponsible parents, and Schools' inability to enforce rules and regulations. The study therefore recommended that the Ministry of Education should intensify monitoring of schools to ensure that teachers and pupils are fully involved or committed to the teaching and learning process. Additionally, Rules and regulations should be realistic and stated clearly for the absorption of all pupils in all secondary schools.

Keywords: Academic Performance; Indiscipline; Negative Attitudes; Pupils; School Rules and Regulations.

1. Introduction

The definition of discipline is replete as much as there are many writers. This implies that the word 'discipline' can assume different meanings depending on the context in which it is used. Gaustard (2015) stated that school discipline is the business of enforcing school rules that facilitate learning and minimize disruption. An effective teacher should involve himself/herself in the bit-by-bit, time-consuming task of helping pupils to see the sense of acting in a certain positive way. Discipline arises from the need to bring about a balance between what an individual wants of others and the restrictions demanded by the society in which we live (Kochhar, 2021). From the time corporal punishment was abolished in Zambian schools, indiscipline cases among pupils seem to have increased. Pupils no longer respect

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teachers, pupils bully other pupils, insult, and they are involved in other activities like beer drinking and smoking. Indiscipline acts among secondary school pupils is a serious problem affecting learning institutions in Zambia and the world over. It is a social and political problem that affects each and every individual in society and the world today. Based on this realization, a number of researchers have conducted some studies to try and find ways of minimizing this trend.

Different authors have defined discipline in various terms. Adesina (1980), says that discipline is to teach the pupils manners show respect to school authorities, observe the school laws and regulations, and maintain an established standard of behavior. From this definition, the school has a primordial role to play in instilling discipline into its students. Therefore, school administrators and teachers should enforce acceptable behavior in their students. Egwunyenga (2005) defined discipline as the training that enables an individual to develop orderly conduct and self-control as well as direction. Peretomode (1995) maintains that discipline involves the ability to have self-control, restraint, respect for self, and respect for others. Discipline according to Abubakar (2000) is the ability and willingness to do what one ought to do without external control. Hence one can say discipline is internally motivated within the individual and depends on the state of mind of an individual. It is voluntary and an individual deliberately makes efforts to conform to an established code of conduct. However, Aguba (2009) while emphasizing Douglas McGregor's theory x, maintained that discipline is externally induced in individuals who do not succumb to established rules and regulations out of personal volition but out of fear of punishment or sanction. Rosen (1997) sees discipline as a branch of knowledge, training that develops self-control, character, orderliness, or efficiency, strict control to enforce obedience and treatment that controls or punishes, and a system of rules. According to Slee (1995), discipline involves teaching and self-control. The United States Department of Education 1993 in Ibid (1997) acknowledges that maintaining a disciplined environment conducive to learning requires an ethics of caring that shapes staff-pupil relations.

Rossouw (2013) says that pupils portray different types of indiscipline behavior among which include the following acts: boycotting lessons, watching and practicing pornography, lies telling, violence, dishonesty, disobedient to teachers, prefects, and school administration, rapping school/classmates, alcohol consumption, and confronting. The critical tool used in the transformation of individuals in particular and society in general. Secondary education in Zambia is meant to prepare the learners for valuable living conditions within the society and training for further education. In order to live a valuable life within any given community and contribute towards the social, economic, and political development of the nation, the appropriate skills, values, attitudes, knowledge, and competencies must be impacted by the individual. The percentage of pupils who drop out of school in most urban and rural areas of Zambia is on the increase. These pupils cultivate and demonstrate deviant behaviors and may never fulfill their potential and in the long run, they become burdens to society (Simata, 2013). There is an outcry from Zambian educators, administrators, and parents about the increasing rate of indiscipline in Zambian secondary schools, specifically in the Lusaka district.

Pupils' indiscipline has been a source of worry for schools, parents, and other stakeholders concerned with the education of children. As Ali et.al (2014) elucidates, indiscipline is a multifaceted phenomenon regarding its displays and causes as well as its meanings and functions in the social, psychosocial, and pedagogical fields. School discipline has two main objectives; first to ensure the safety of staff members and pupils and second to create an environment conducive to learning (Gaustard, 2015). As Madziyire (2012) argues, effective discipline is needed in school for good academic achievement because when there is effective discipline in a school and in the classroom, effective teaching and learning can take place. The cases of indiscipline in Zambian secondary schools are very widespread, ranging from minor cases like late coming, bullying, and stealing to major cases like prostitution and drug abuse Ncube (2013). Most schools have well-crafted school rules and yet in spite of these rules, the phenomenon of indiscipline persists. With the introduction of free education by the United Party for National Development (UPND) government, most secondary schools are overwhelmed with the huge number of pupils who enrolled especially in secondary schools found in Lusaka district. This leads to overcrowded classrooms and due to this, indiscipline cases among pupils seem to be on the rise.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

Discipline plays a key role in the management of schools. Among pupils in schools, it helps them to acquire quality education (Ndakwa, 2020). In Zambian schools, offices that deal with discipline cases have been opened. Many other measures have been put in place to combat indiscipline acts in the learning environment. Other efforts taken to ensure a good learning environment and behavioral modification of pupils include that of in-service management training of the administrators. School managers and their deputies are provided with in-service management refresher training courses to equip them with knowledge and skills for handling various issues in

their workplaces (Nyaga, 2014). Despite all the measures put in place, indiscipline cases seem to be escalating at an alarming rate. This has led to the ill academic achievement of pupils in Lusaka district and the entire country at large. This has also made it difficult for the school teachers and management team to smoothly run the schools. If this trend is left unattended, it might deteriorate the quality of education in Zambia. It is for this reason that the study found keen interest in analyzing the factors leading to high levels of indiscipline cases among pupils in secondary schools of Lusaka district.

1.2. The Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to analyze factors leading to high levels of indiscipline among pupils in secondary schools in Lusaka district, Zambia.

1.3. Research Objectives

The objectives of the study were to:

- Examine factors leading to high levels of indiscipline cases among pupils in secondary schools in Lusaka district, Zambia.
- Assess the effect of pupils' indiscipline behavior on the management of secondary schools in Lusaka district, Zambia.
- Suggest measures that can be put in place to curb indiscipline behavior among pupils in secondary schools in Lusaka district, Zambia.

1.4. Theoretical Framework

This study was guided by the Behaviorism Theory. This theory postulates that learning has nothing to do with the mind (Jason, 2015). In fact, learning occurs with the acquisition of new behavior. It was introduced by B.F. Skinner one of the behaviorist psychologists says that a measurable learning outcome is only possible if we change the learner's behavior Dewald (2019). Behaviorists rely only on observable behavior in order to learn. They do not focus their attention on the mental activities of the learners, because to them learning happens when certain conditions are met. These conditions i.e. behaviors are universal in nature. To behaviorists, learning comes from observation of cultures Henry (2015). It comes from the environment. The major problems facing the world today can be solved only if we improve our understanding of human behavior Ibid (2015). There must be some incentive to create certain responses. According to behaviorism, the incentive may either be positive or negative. If it is the former then the learner will be rewarded, while if it is the latter, the learner will be punished (Lisa, 2013).

1.5. Significance of the Study

It is hoped that the findings of this study would bring to light on the causes and effects of indiscipline cases among pupils in secondary schools of Lusaka district. This information may be useful to the policymakers and curriculum developers in coming up with strategies that may be implemented in schools in order to minimize the high rates of indiscipline cases among pupils. The study findings may also aid in strengthening quality education and improving the academic performance of pupils in secondary schools.

2. Literature review

2.1. Nature of Indiscipline Among Pupils in Secondary Schools

Acts of indiscipline among pupils in schools have been repeatedly noted in Zambia and elsewhere. These acts have become an issue in learning institutions. Kochhar (2021) upholds that indiscipline is conceptualized as a behavior that breaches the rules and regulations of a school, and later undermines its effectiveness. Therefore, it takes discipline to blend and advance development at both the personal and the national level. Various forms of pupil indiscipline cases are increasingly reported all around the globe. Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2019) indicates the frequency of certain pupil misbehavior amongst secondary school pupils in England, Italy, Japan, Russia, Scotland, and the USA. According to the report, problems of indiscipline in these countries include absenteeism, arriving late at school, skipping class periods, violating dress code, classroom disturbances, cheating, vandalism, theft, and inflicting physical injuries on other students. In America, Clarke (2012) in the study of discipline in schools, reported a number of pupil indiscipline cases that include violence upon teachers and other students, possession of controlled substances such as alcohol, robbery, engaging in habitual profanity, vulgarity, committing school assault to staff and

making terrorist threats against the school authority. In the same manner, Parkay (2016) upholds that the most pressing social problem confronting schools in the USA is the abuse of illegal drugs, tobacco, and alcohol.

Consequently, UNESCO (2018) reported that unruly classrooms around the world had reached a very alarming proportion. With incidences reported from various places of the world. According to the report, killings, physical attacks, robberies, and fighting are some of the tragedies that make headlines around the world. The report further noted school violence is becoming common in a number of countries. Cotton (2013) asserts that American classrooms were frequently plagued by misbehavior which disrupted the flow of classroom activities and interfered with learning. Along the same line, Onyechi et al (2017) point out that the Trends International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) shows that pupil misbehavior in the classroom was perceived by head teachers to be the most frequently occurring problem in most countries. This calls for adequate disciplinary measures to normalize the situation. Rhalmi (2020) states that “discipline is paramount for every learning and essential for any teaching.” The article goes on to say “Discipline is important for peace and harmony in any learning environment, this takes an account of peace between students, teachers, and administration. In the classroom, discipline is regarded as a code of conduct that both teachers and students agree upon and cooperate in its enforcement. It brings about cooperation and settlement in classroom management. The condition of pupil indiscipline in Jamaica is very similar to the one in the USA. Policymakers, administrators, teachers, parents, and the public have been struggling to find lasting solutions to the problem of indiscipline in schools. Stubbing, killings, and assaults were features of life in many school communities (INTO, 2020). Pupils went on strikes, resorted to copying and cheating in examinations, insulted their teachers, tore away pages from the library books, wrote dirty things on the walls, and practiced violence under any pretext (Rahul, 2011).

2.2. The Concept of Pupil Indiscipline

Indiscipline among pupils today is a common thing, it is said to have its origin in the society in which a pupil lives, it is also said to have its roots in the brain of a student and also in the institution that the learner is (Selby, 2018). Indiscipline in most cases has affected the academic of most pupils and also influenced them negatively. It is a factor that should be taken seriously because it has affected effective learning in most schools and hindered the academic performance of most students. There should be discipline in every institution and the administration of the school through the B.O.G should always implement rules that students should follow and also take action to students who misbehave to ensure there is proper functioning of the school. In many schools the student who has excelled and achieved their set goals the result of proper discipline and have been able to improve their personality not only in school but also are able to cope with the society they come from due to the fact that good discipline is the life and soul of a student. Students who are well-focused in schools are always beyond others in terms of academic achievement. Student discipline is therefore a factor that should always be fully embraced by pupils in schools in order to achieve their objectives in education and excel academically.

2.3. Influence of Peer Pressure on Pupil Indiscipline

Most of the students who are greatly affected by peer pressure are the students who have lacked confidence in their self and even some who have lacked self-respect hence depending on others. Their behaviors are highly affected because of their dependency on others hence in schools most pupils who have indiscipline have adopted the behavior of others and are mostly persuaded to do an act by the others Rahul (2011). Mostly pupils in schools who are undisciplined should their disruptive behaviors when they are with their peers and do not do them when they are alone Azizi (2019). In most schools, peers influence others to bring chaos and this is a result of interaction with those who have different behaviors with negative influence (Ndakwa 2020). On the other hand, Thomas (2020) in his research points out that most pupils who are disciplined are mostly pushed by their friends whenever they are together and that they always have the freedom to manifest a lack of discipline. Matsoga (2013) further state that in different schools lack of discipline among student is a result of some student instilling more pressure on others to emulate their behavior. Undesirable behavior as a result of peer pressure includes strikes and poor dress codes that don't observe school rules. Rossouw (2013) points out that most form of indiscipline in schools is socially learned when peers form a group which always have a negative impact. Most of the pupil's self-concept and how they see themselves has been affected by peers. Most teenagers want to be loved and feel they belong and always make every effort even if it means doing wrong to be accepted by others (Barassa, 2013).

2.4. Influence of Mass Media on Pupil Indiscipline

Media has become one of the factors that has influenced pupil behavior, these include TV, radio, and electric media like mobile phones and computers Kimani (2014) Mass media can influence student behavior positively and also negatively but a case in most secondary it has highly contributed to student indiscipline. Most of the students have been involved in mass media hence disrupting their behavior and this includes the cyber media which are said to have a negative influence. Most young people especially pupils have engaged in the use of social media platforms like the useful of

Facebook and the content posted has always had a negative influence on the person's behavior Coombs (2020). A research study done by Muide (2015) has shown that one way the media influences the behavior of pupils is through content that most of the young pupils watch on TV, she indicated that most teenagers enjoy watching content that has a negative impact like programs about drug abuse, and theft. These shows that are aired always instill temptations to most young pupils to put into practice what they have watched. Entertainment done on most media platforms always interferes with the personality of most pupils. Mimaita (2013) point that sexual content always alters the behavior of most student since most of the student are always forced to engage in sexual behaviors. According to Daily Nation (2019) students were arrested and detained by the police for watching pornographic videos online, this was a form of indiscipline that the student displayed and portrayed the influence of media. Muide (2015) in his study state that most of the student in schools have engaged in exam irregularities whereby student have used the internet to leak most of the exams and teachers have caught most of them engaging in cheating. Bandura (1985) states that most people even students are always involved with the actions they watch, they can be depicted by what they watch in media like aggressiveness by people in TV shows and movies can make them also aggressive.

2.5. Drug Abuse and Pupil Indiscipline in Schools

According to (Daily Nation April 14 2019 page 7) a report done by the National survey on alcohol in secondary schools indicated that the drugs that are commonly used by pupils are khat, bhang, and alcohol and have been popular to many pupils with 23.4% of the young pupils consuming it including both gender. A report done by NACADA 2019 show that most pupils have abused drugs in most schools, the drugs that are consumed in schools 29.3% originate from student carrying them to school, 25.7% of some of the pupils who consume drug buy them from others and it's against school rules to sell and buy drugs, 19.3% of student are able to get the drugs from nearby brew dens and the student who have consumed this drugs are of young age in schools. In his study, Nyaga (2014) points out that pupils who are involved in drug abuse in schools mostly break school rules like being absent from classes making them complete their education for a long duration. Most of these deviant behaviors like truancy, and fighting have culminated in drug abuse hence hindering the performance of most pupils in schools, hence making them student abusers Robert (2012). Daily Nation (Feb. 25 2019 page 10) stated that pupils have highly been involved in consuming drugs like kuber making them involved in criminal activity a case whereby some of them have gone to the extent of beating their teachers under the influence of the drug.

3. Methodology

3.1. Study Design

Exploratory and descriptive designs were considered appropriate as they allowed for more flexible strategies for data collection in order to answer the research questions The study also adopted a mixed methods approach, combining the quantitative and qualitative data. The study was aimed at collecting information from respondents on the factors leading to high levels of indiscipline cases among pupils in secondary schools of Lusaka district in Zambia.

3.2. Research Site

The research was conducted in Lusaka district of Zambia at six selected secondary schools from which respondents were also sampled.

3.3. Population, Sample and Sampling Procedure

The population for the study comprised head teachers, teachers, and pupils from the targeted schools. The target population was 3000. The sample size involved a total of 300 respondents which included six (6) head teachers, one from each selected school. Eighteen (18) teachers, three from each selected school, and Two Hundred Seventy-six (276) pupils, Forty-six (46) from each selected school. The study employed both purposive and simple random sampling on different participants from the selected secondary schools.

3.4. Data Analysis

In this research, data was analyzed qualitatively as the semi-structured interview schedules were used as data collection instruments. A thematic approach was used, where data analysis started with the categorization of themes from the semi-structured interview schedules. The data gathered was analyzed according to the themes of the study and the order of the research objectives. Data generated from the questionnaires was analyzed manually and also with a combination of software MS Access, SPSS, and MS Excel. Analysis of the data in this study was mainly descriptive in nature.

3.5. Ethical Issues

To obtain the population of the study, data collection, and dissemination of the findings, the researcher was sensitive to research ethics and its values. This helped to ensure that a good image of the research enterprise in the world was maintained. Alternatively, informed consent, and assent were obtained from respondents involved in the research, and the research topic was strategically selected to ensure that there was no harm whatsoever to the research respondents. No name for the participants was required, participants were free to withdraw if they wanted to and were assured of confidentiality and anonymity. Additionally, the researchers got permission from Lusaka DEBS Office, and the head teachers on behalf of the independent schools.

4. Results and discussions

The following findings and discussions were presented according to set research objectives:

4.1. Factors Leading to High Levels of Indiscipline Cases Among Pupils in Secondary Schools

Table 1 Responses from the Teachers

Teacher 's views	Frequency	Percentage
Negative attitudes towards education	2	22.2%
Influence of peers	3	33.3%
Irresponsible parents	1	11.1%
Schools' inability to enforce rules and regulations	2	22.2%
Total	9	100

Based on research objective one, it was clear that teachers and pupils believed that indiscipline is majorly caused by the influence of peers supported by 33.3% of teachers and also supported by 35% of the pupils. Other causes of indiscipline included; Negative attitudes towards education (22.2%), Irresponsible parents (11.1%), and Schools' inability to enforce rules and regulations (22.2%). It is important to note that the causes of indiscipline are mostly linked to school administrations and teachers and this agrees with the findings of Gaustard (2015) who states that the inefficient administration of school causes disorders, dissatisfaction and undisciplined behaviors among pupils. The result also agrees with (Kochhar2021) who opines that some principals are generally bad administrators who do not know some basic elements of administration techniques.

Table 2 Responses from the Pupils

Pupil 's views	Frequency	Percentage
Negative attitudes towards education	9	30%
Influence of peers	12	40%
Overcrowded classes	6	20%
Schools' inability to enforce rules and regulations	3	10%
Total	30	100

Elsewhere, Asiyai (2012) supported this view in his postulation that schools' inability to enforce rules and regulations causes indiscipline through the lack of certain rules in schools. Asiyai also said that many pupils become mischievous in the classroom because the class has not outlined the classroom rules. Also, monotonous and uninteresting teaching makes pupils bored and restive and poor lesson presentation due to lack of preparation can also result in a lack of interest and can prompt undisciplined behavior. They can neither establish nor maintain good communication with their staff or pupils. Such would not know the appropriate measures to take in times of emergency. Similarly, Clarke (2012) opined that indiscipline in schools results from the school administration, the principal's unnecessary strictness, even the principals' failure to have a cordial relationship with staff, and also lack of adequate communication between staff and pupils. There are numerous causes of pupils' indiscipline as put forward by some schools. Most of these causes

are attributed to some factors such as parental neglect of pupils from home. Lack of guidance and counseling given to pupils in schools by teachers and also poor content of curriculum for pupils.

4.1.1. Pupils Form of Indiscipline in Secondary Schools as Identified by Teachers

Table 3 Different Forms of Indiscipline

Indiscipline behaviour	Frequency	Percentage
Absenteeism	4	44.4%
Late coming	2	22.2%
Use of bad Languages	1	11.1%
Theft	2	22.2%
Total	9	100

On different forms of indiscipline, it was discovered that absenteeism took the major form of pupils’ indiscipline in secondary schools. Other forms of indiscipline included; late coming use of bad Language and theft. Not only that, another factor such as fighting, was also given upper rank although it was not very much considered in this discussion. The findings of combined responses of the head teachers, teachers, and pupils indicated that a lot should be done to discover other forms of pupils’ indiscipline. This is true because for normal learning to be in place, the level of pupils’ indiscipline should be reduced. Bedding (2016) says that teachers work better in school when the pupils are disciplined.

4.2. Effects of Pupils' Indiscipline Behavior on the Management of Secondary Schools

Figure 1 Responses from the Head Teachers on The Effects of Pupils' Indiscipline Behavior on the Management of Secondary Schools

Indiscipline among pupils in secondary schools can have various negative effects on both individuals and the overall school environment. The results showed that the effects of indiscipline in pupils’ academic performance leads to poor performance of pupils that tarnishes the school image, indiscipline results in poor academic performance, indiscipline among secondary school students affects teachers’ efficiency, nonchalant attitude among secondary school students leads to principal’s/teachers ineffectiveness, and pupils’ indiscipline affects parent-teacher relationship. The study found that indiscipline often leads to a lack of focus on academic activities and pupils may skip classes, neglect homework, and perform poorly in exams. Simatwa (2017) affirmed this by stressing that low academic achievers are undisciplined and uncommitted members of the school organization. He stated that ‘if members of a given system are

dissatisfied, uninvolved and uncommitted to its basic aims and expectations, they will find it easier to engage in behavior disapproved by the system than those who are satisfied, involved and committed to its basic aims. Indiscipline behavior, such as talking back to teachers or disruptive actions, can disturb the learning atmosphere. Other pupils may find it challenging to concentrate in a disruptive classroom, affecting their own academic progress. Corroborating this, Kgari (2015) opined that society is passing through a very difficult time and the incidence of indiscipline permeates the entire social economic, and political life as a nation. Similarly, Rosen (1997) identified indiscipline as a major cause that brings about low academic attainment in schools. Rosen stressed that in times past students exhibited the best behavior wherever they were. They respected their teachers and obeyed them, they feared failing examinations and so, worked very hard, but today the reverse is the case. All these according to Rosen boil down to low academic performance. Furthermore, teachers may face challenges in managing classrooms and maintaining control if there is a prevalence of indiscipline. One of the teachers stressed that constant disruptions can lead to increased stress and burnout among teachers. The study further found that indiscipline can strain relationships among pupils in the sense that bullying, teasing, and conflicts may arise due to disruptive behavior, leading to an unhealthy social environment. Hence, indiscipline in secondary school may contribute to the development of long-term behavioral problems and pupils who engage in disruptive behavior may be more prone to involvement in delinquent activities outside of school.

4.3. Measures to Curb Indiscipline Behavior Among Pupils in Secondary Schools

Figure 2 Measures to Curb Indiscipline Behavior Among Pupils in Secondary Schools

On ways of reducing pupils' indiscipline in secondary schools, the data reflected that the major and appropriate way of reducing indiscipline was through giving guidance and counseling to pupils in schools. Other ways of reducing indiscipline in the schools were also revealed such as developing self-direction and self-control in pupils, developing rules and regulations, rewarding and recognizing pupils who do good things in school among others. Onyechi et al (2017) explain that counseling helps pupils by increasing their self-awareness, emotional growth, and maturity. Counselling also empowers them to articulate their issues, as there is more understanding of their problems. The students are empowered as they explore alternative solutions to their problems. They learn the need to explore the advantages and disadvantages of the choices they make (Azizi, 2019). Pupils consequently learn to be more accountable for their actions. It was found out that counseling strategies utilized by public secondary school principals in controlling indiscipline among students included: ensuring the new students are properly given orientation on the right way to behave in school, ensuring that students have individual or group counseling sessions with a counselor every term for proper guidance and supporting counselor's commendations for change that will help an unruly pupil, while the counselling strategies.

School discipline is a system of certain rules that are considered appropriate to regulate behavior and maintain order among the school-going children (Ali, et al, 2014). The term also refers to the code of behavior commonly known as School Rules and Regulations. These rules may include the expected standards of clothing, timekeeping, social behavior, and work ethic. School discipline often is enforced through the application of punishment which results from breaking the code of behavior. Often school discipline becomes a means of administration of punishment, rather than behaving within the school rules. The means of Punishment often turn abusive and it is here that School Discipline becomes controversial and raises its ugly head (Kgari 2015). The aim of school discipline is to create a safe and happy learning environment in the classroom. When a teacher is unable to maintain order and discipline in the classroom, students may become unmotivated and distressed, and the climate for learning is diminished, leading to underachievement. Discipline is a necessary part of school life and Methods of maintaining discipline in schools are not always successful (Mgomezulu, 2013). Indiscipline among children is common in all schools, although most schools manage to contain it to tolerable limits. However, at times, poor disciplinary management within the school can cause a general breakdown in order. This disorder often results in violence against teachers and other children.

5. Conclusion

Addressing indiscipline in schools requires a comprehensive and collaborative approach involving teachers, parents, and the wider school community. It's essential to create an environment that not only corrects undesirable behavior but also promotes the development of responsible and disciplined individuals. Based on the findings of this study, it is imperative to note that indiscipline is a problem for everyone and has an effect on all aspects of human lives, and as such everyone must be involved in curbing indiscipline. Also, schools should reawaken their main objective which is to reform the human mind and perspective of life, instilling discipline and teaching the human mind the need for good social behavior. According to the study's findings of the problems, the results of the data collected and analyzed, therefore revealed that the negative influence of peers is the major cause of pupils' indiscipline in Secondary schools. However, many other explanations that had been not of immediate interest to the study might also have a bearing on the causes of pupils' indiscipline in secondary schools, such factors as incompetent teachers, overcrowded classrooms lack of rules and regulations, and so on.

Recommendations

The following are actions that should be taken on the basis of the findings of this study:

- The Zambian Government through the Ministry of Education should monitor schools and ensure that teachers and students are fully involved or committed to the teaching and learning process.
- The Ministry of Education should regularly assess and monitor the effectiveness of discipline policies and interventions in secondary schools.
- The Zambian Government through the Ministry of Education should come up with policies that involve Guidance and counseling services to be offered to pupils by teachers, Head teachers, and parents from within and outside the school environment.
- School administrators should ensure that the school policies do not push the pupils to the point of rebellion, instead rules and regulations should be realistic and stated clearly for the absorption of all pupils.
- School administrators should encourage teachers to use positive discipline strategies that focus on reinforcing good behavior rather than just punishing misconduct.
- School administrators should maintain open lines of communication with parents and involve them in addressing indiscipline.
- School administrators should ensure that teachers and staff serve as positive role models for pupils.
- There is a need for pupils who show good behavior in school to be rewarded and recognized positively by the school administration to motivate other pupils to show good behavior at all times.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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